

Cloning and Molecular Characterization of Coat Protein Gene (CP) of *Tomato Leaf Curl New Delhi Virus* (G : Begomovirus, F : Geminiviridae) in Ridge Gourd and *In silico* Analysis of the BR1 Family of Coat Protein

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ABSTRACT

Ridge gourd is cultivated in tropical, subtropical and few varieties like Pusa Nasdar and Satputia temperate regions across the world. It is a rich source of essential vitamins and minerals around the world. However, the production of ridge gourd has been severely affected by diseases among which viral diseases have major impact on its production. The viral disease caused by *tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus* (ToLCNDV), a member of the genus *Begomovirus*, family Geminiviridae-an economically important virus affecting the ridge gourd yield. It is transmitted by the whiteflies [*Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius)] and causes ridge gourd yellow mosaic disease (RgYMD) in ridge gourds. The present study mainly aimed at the process of development of *Agrobacterium* coat protein gene construct and *in silico* analysis of CP. The total DNA from infected leaves of ridge gourd with ToLCNDV was amplified using CP specific primers with amplicon size of 771bp. The purified CP gene was successfully cloned to the TA cloning vector. The CP gene was further moved into plant expression binary vector pBI121. The gene construct of the plant expression vector was transformed into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. *In-silico* analysis of the coat protein revealed that the protein contains nuclear export factors BR1 family. BLAST results analysis of coat protein with respect to the other coat proteins of ToLCNDV depicted 80-90 per cent resemblance. Phylogenetic tree revealed the common origin of this protein.

Keywords : Ridge gourd, ToLCNDV, CP gene, *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, *In-silico* analysis, BLAST

RIDGE gourd [*Luffa acutangula* (L.) Roxb.] - Loofah, (Family: Cucurbitaceae) is a popular vegetable crop in India and other Asian and Western countries like Europe. It contains a surplus amount of fiber, vitamins and minerals including Vitamin B2, Vitamin C, carotene, niacin, calcium, phosphorus, iron and small quantities of iodine and fluorine. Ridge gourd has been used in Indian traditional system as medicines in the form of diuretic, expectorant, laxative, purgative, hypoglycemic agent and bitter tonic. It harbors many phytochemicals such as flavonoids, oleanolic acid, saponins, luffangulin, sapogenin and cucurbitacin

(Manikandaselvi *et al.*, 2016).

At present, the emergence of ridge gourd yellow mosaic disease (RgYMD) caused by *tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus* (ToLCNDV) is becoming the major constraint for ridge gourd production. An absolute complete devastation of the crop was observed at the seedling stage of virus infection. ToLCNDV is a member of the begomovirus family and infests various economically important plant species, including weeds, vegetable and ornamental species. The isolates of the virus are transmitted by the whiteflies (*Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius)). In a study

done on coat protein by Likhith and Peter (2023), on the interaction between Coat Protein (CP) of *Tomato leaf curl virus* (ToLCV) and its host whitefly it was seen that during the process of transmission, CP interacts with the whitefly proteins in the digestive tract, midgut, haemolymph and salivary glands. This disease was first reported in tomatoes followed by other crops which belong to the family Solanaceae and Cucurbitaceae. Other cucurbitaceous crops species like cucumber, sponge gourd, watermelon, bitter gourd and pumpkin are also naturally infected by ToLCNDV with symptoms such as typical mosaic with light chlorotic areas on the leaf lamina, yellow, pale green intermingled (mosaic) with normal green tissues, reduction in the size of the leaf, stunting of plant, upward curling and blistering of leaves. In a study by Rajeshwari and Reddy (2014), diseased bottle gourd plants which were infected by Tomato Leaf Curl New Delhi Virus were transmitted readily and in a long lasting manner by the whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci*. ToLCNDV infection notably affects plant growth and thereby reduces the production and productivity. The farmers are managing the disease infection by controlling the white flies in the field through the application of chemical insecticides which may develop resistance to pesticides in the near future. Therefore, an alternative approach needs to be developed for the efficient control of the virus. The major approach for efficient control of viral diseases can be obtained by using the genes derived from the pathogen itself. This mechanism is called pathogen derived resistance (PDR). In PDR, the protection of the plants is obtained through the expression of nucleotide sequences derived from the genome of the plant viruses. Coat protein-mediated resistance (CP-MR) is one of the important PDR mechanisms in which the resistance is imparted to the transgenic plants that produce coat protein to impart resistance against the virus from which the CP gene is derived. From the past years, the transgenic plants are usually developed using coat protein mediated resistance. ToLCNDV is ssDNA virus it has two genome components, named DNA A and DNA B. The genes in the virion and complementary sense orientations on DNA A and DNA B are separated by an intergenic region containing a common region (CR) (Padidam

et al., 1995). The ToLCNDV DNA A encodes a replication associated protein (Rep; from AC1), a replication enhancer protein [REn; from AC2 open reading frame (ORF)], a transcriptional activator protein (TrAP; from AC3), a coat protein (CP; from AV1), an AV2 protein and an AC4 protein. DNA B encodes a movement protein (MP; from BCI) and a nuclear shuttle protein (NSP; from BVI) (Fondong, 2013). There can be re assortment and component capture, which are seemingly very common in begomoviruses and are most likely the major mechanisms in begomoviruses, adapted to infect new hosts (Lefeuvre and Moriones, 2015).

The characterization of BR1 family of CP gene of ToLCNDV has not been done so far in any cucurbits crop. However, mutagenesis studies on MSV coat protein (Liu *et al.*, 1999) and TYLCV (Kunik *et al.*, 1998) indicated that the NLS region resulted in the cytoplasmic accumulation of the mutant protein. In a study by Kumar *et al.* (2012) pairwise sequence alignment of NLS region from MSV and ToLCGV-[Vad] coat proteins resulted in an identity and similarity percentage of 25 per cent and 33.3 per cent with a score of '6 whereas TYLCV and ToLCGV-[Vad] yielded an identity and similarity percentage of 51.7 per cent and 58.6 per cent with a score of 49 suggesting that ToLCV coat protein is much more conserved with TYLCV rather than a representative protein member of BR1 family (pfam00844) in Pfam database. Thus BR1 family gives an idea about the conserved regions of the CP genes, which can be extrapolated to understand the infectivity of the virus.

There were no stable resistant varieties against ToLCNDV which is developed so far. Hence, in the present research paper, we are reporting the development of *Agrobacterium* with CP gene construct and *in-silico* analysis of CP genes. This gene construct can be further used for the development of resistant ridge gourd cultivars.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of ToLCNDV Infected Ridge Gourd Samples and DNA Extraction

Infected ridge gourd samples (Variety Arka Prasanna) were collected from Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hesaraghatta.

Fig. 1 : Infected ridge gourd samples

DNA Extraction

Total genomic DNA was isolated from the infected leaves by using CTAB method (Doyle 1990). The leaves were collected, grounded in autoclaved mortar and pestle by the addition of liquid nitrogen and homogenized with CTAB extraction buffer (preheated for 15 minutes at 65 °C). The sample was transferred to a 1.5 mL micro centrifuge tube and was incubated in a water bath for one hour at 65 °C. The tubes were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for fifteen minutes, pellet was discarded and in the supernatant chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1) was added to the tube and mixed by inversion, spun for a minute and supernatant was transferred to a new 1.5 mL tube. 0.5 mL of chilled absolute alcohol along with 0.1 volume of 3M Sodium acetate or 7.5 M ammonium acetate was added to the new tubes and it was incubated in - 20 °C overnight, Next day, the tubes were again centrifuged at 13000 rpm for ten minutes. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet was washed with 70 per cent ethanol. The pellets were kept for drying for few minutes and then dissolved in 50 µL sterile nuclease free water and then stored at - 20 °C.

Bacterial Strain and Vector

The CP of ToLCNDV was cloned into the TA cloning vector, followed by binary vector pBI121 at the Xba I at 5' end and Sac I at 3' and mobilized into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain GV3101 by a freeze-thaw method (Holsters *et al.*, 1978). The coat protein gene (CP) was driven by the cauliflower

mosaic virus (CaMV) 35 S promoter. The bacterial strain *E.coli* DH5 α was grown overnight in Luria broth (LB) medium with appropriate antibiotics and collected in the log phase, when the absorbance at 550 nm was between 0.4 - 0.8.

PCR Analysis of CP Gene

Genomic DNA was isolated from the putatively transformed plants by CTAB method (Doyle 1990). Primers were designed using the available database from NCBI (Accession ID EU366163.1). The CP gene primers are primer 1 (sense) 5' TCTAGAATGGC GAAGCGACC 3' corresponding to the N - terminal sequence of CP gene and primer 2 (antisense) 5' GGTACCTTAATTTGTTACCG 3' corresponding to the C - terminal sequence of CP gene. PCR amplification was carried out with ten micro liter reaction mixtures for each sample. The PCR master mix was prepared fresh and in bulk for all samples - Takara PCR master mix (2x Premix) - 5.0 µL, Forward primer (10 pmol /µL) - 0.5 µL, Reverse primer (10 pmol/µL) - 0.5 µL, template DNA - 1.0 µL (100ng), nuclease free water - 3.0 µL. DNA was subjected to 35 cycles of 1 min at 92 °C, 1 min at 55 °C and 1 min at 72 °C. Amplified DNA fragments were separated on a 0.8 per cent agarose ethidium bromide gel and observed under ultraviolet light.

Cloning of CP Gene into TA Cloning Vector

Competent cells of *E.coli* DH5 α were prepared and the tube containing competent cells was removed from the - 80 °C freezer and kept briefly in ice for thawing (Chang *et al.*, 2017). Ligation mixture (10 µL) was added to 100 µL of competent cells and incubated in ice for 30 min. The cells were subjected to heat shock at 42 °C for 1 min and snap - chilled on ice for 10 min. Sterile Luria Bertani (LB broth - HiMedia) (1 mL) was added to cells and grown at 37 °C for 2h in a shaking incubator at 120 rpm. After incubation the cells were spun at 6,000 rpm and dissolved in 100 µL of LB broth and plated on LB agar (HiMedia) plates containing ampicillin (50 µg/mL), 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl-beta-D- galacto-pyranoside (X-gal) (20 mg/mL)

and Isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) (100 mM) and incubated overnight at 37 °C. The TA cloning vector (pTZ57R/T) used in cloning was compatible for blue-white screening when plated on X-gal and IPTG. The recombinant clones with a foreign DNA insert ligated at the 3' - ddT overhangs disrupt the reading frame of lac-Z and produce white colonies whereas, the self-ligated (circularized) vector produces blue colonies due to enzymatic activity of lac-Z on the substrate X-gal. Colony PCR of transformed recombinant vectors was done and the colonies were picked for plasmid isolation. Further, PCR amplification of plasmid DNA was done for confirmation. Further, the orientation of the *CP* gene in the vector was confirmed by restriction digestion.

Cloning and Transformation of *CP* Gene into pBI121 Plant Expression Vector

Single colony of pBI121 and transformed pTZ57R/T + *CP* was inoculated and grown overnight in 10 mL LB broth at 37 °C with appropriate antibiotics. The plasmid was isolated and the quantity and quality of isolated plasmid was estimated using Nanodrop. The vector pBI121 and transformed pTZ57R/T + *CP* were double digested with *Xba* I and *Sac* I restriction enzymes. The reaction mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 1 hour followed by 65 °C for heat inactivation. The digested products were run on 1.5 per cent agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide and visualized in UV- transilluminator. Elution of DNA from agarose gel was done and the plasmid pBI121 ~13kb and *CP* gene of ~771bp (Digested from vector pTZ57R/T + *CP*) DNA fragment were excised from the agarose gel under UV-transilluminator. Further, ligation of digested products (vector and insert) was done using ligase enzyme (200 U/ μ L). The reaction mixture was incubated at 16 °C for 16 hours. Transformation of *E. coli* cells to express coat protein gene was done and the Colony PCR of transformed recombinant vector to pick the recombinants was performed further. Amplified PCR product was run on 1.0 per cent (w/v) agarose gel and visualized in UV-transilluminator.

Transformation of pBI121 + *CP* Vector into *Agrobacterium Tumefaciens*

The competent cells of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* were prepared by taking a single colony of *Agrobacterium* strain GV3101 from a freshly streaked YEP agar plate which was inoculated into 5 mL YEP broth containing rifampicin (50 μ g/mL) and was subsequently grown under controlled conditions for 48 hours until the OD600 reaches 0.5 - 0.6 and the transformation was carried out by heat shock method with the help of competent cells. The competent cell and plasmid DNA mixture was dipped in liquid nitrogen for 5 minutes followed by heat shock which was given to the transformation tube by placing the bottom half of the tube into a 37 °C water bath for 5 min. After that the tubes were kept back on ice for 2-5 min. YEP broth (1 ml) was added to the tube and incubated at 28 °C in the shaker incubator at 160 rpm for 4 - 6 hrs. Then culture tubes were centrifuged at 5000 rpm 2-3 min and the pellet were re-suspended in the 100 μ L broth. The plating was done with antibiotic Kanamycin (50 μ g/mL) and rifampicin and incubated at 28 °C for 48 h. Further, colony PCR, plasmid isolation and confirmation of transformation by plasmid PCR was done.

Analyses of Putative Functions Domains in Coat Protein

The functional domain of the coat protein was extracted from https://www.genome.jp/tools-bin/search_motif_lib (from NCBI). Analysis of the function was done.

Comparison of Geminivirus Coat Protein/Nuclear Export Factor BR1 Family with other Viruses

Using <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/services/rest/fasta/result/fasta-I20230612-102928-0217-18925628-p2m/visual-svg> (from NCBI), the comparison of coat protein/nuclear export factor BR1 family of most of the ToLCNDV infected plants was done. This gives an automated result containing the amino acid sequences. The coloured data can be analyzed manually. The list includes the coat protein/nuclear

export factor BR1 family of most of the ToLCNDV infected plants already fed in the database. The comparison of our data was done with this.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PCR Analysis of CP Gene in Infected Ridge Gourd Samples

The infected ridge gourd samples amplified against 771 bp (Plate 1) which depicts the presence of the viral genome within the sample. This amplification confirmed the presence of ToLCNDV in ridge gourd, Arka Prasanna. Naganur *et al.* (2023) performed the immunocapture - PCR and immunocapture - LAMP assays to capture the virus particles directly from the supernatant obtained from ToLCNDV infected plant sap of ridge gourd. They produced and reported an amplicon of the size of 771 nt from ToLCNDV-Rg-infected ridge gourd samples but not from healthy samples and water control. Similarly, 771 nt size amplicons were observed in begomovirus-infected bitter gourd, bottle gourd, cucumber, pumpkin, ridge gourd, snake gourd and watermelon samples, but not in chilli, capsicum, cowpea and french bean and healthy samples using ToLCNDV-CP specific primers.

Plate 1 : Amplification of antiviral CP gene of using gene specific primers

Lane M : 100 bp marker; Lane 1-6 : amplified CP gene from infected plants

Analysis of CP Gene in pBI121

PCR analysis of the construct prepared in *Escherichia coli* produced an expected amplicon of approximately 771 bp using ToLCNDV CP gene-specific primers (Plate 2). Restriction digestion of the construct using

Plate 2 : Confirmation of positive transformants by PCR amplification using gene specific primers

Lane M : 100 bp Marker; Lane + : Positive transformants, Lane 1, 2 : Confirmed transformants

Plate 3 : Digestion of transformed pB4NU + CP of ToLCNDV with Xba I and Sac I, yields ~ 14kb vector and ~ 800 bp gene.

Lane M : 1 kb Marker; Lane 1, 2 : vector pB4NU + CP of ToLCNDV.

Plate 4 : PCR confirmation of CP gene in plant expression vector pBI121

Lane M : 100 bp Marker; Lane 1 : Amplified CP gene

Xba I and *Sac* I restriction enzymes released a band of approximately 771 bp (ToLCNDV RgCP) gene from the 14.75-Kb vector confirming the recombinant nature of the plasmid (Plate 3). Further, PCR confirmation of insertion of *CP* gene into plant expression vector pBI121 was done (Plate 4).

Analysis of Putatively Transformed *Agrobacterium* GV3101 Strain with *CP* Gene Construct

The plasmid gene construct of pBI121 with *CP* gene was transferred to *Agrobacterium* and it was further confirmed by colony PCR. The presence of *CP* gene in *Agrobacterium* with the amplicon size of 771bp was confirmed (Plate 5).

Plate 5: Colony PCR of transformed *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* GV3101
Lane M: 100 bp Marker; Lane 1-6: Confirmed transformants

In-silico Analysis of the *CP* Gene Sequence

Functional Domains in Coat Protein

Geminivirus Coat Protein/Nuclear Export Factor BR1 Family

The member BR1 has been found to be the protein predominantly present in the *CP* gene of ToLCNDV of ridge gourd (Fig.2) and the amino acid sequence of the protein is depicted in Fig. 3. This facilitates the export of both ds and ss DNA from the nucleus. It has been shown that the 104 N-terminal amino acids of the *maize streak virus* resembles the ToLCNDV coat protein and binds DNA non- specifically. This family also includes various geminivirus movement proteins that are nuclear export factors or shuttles. ToLCV coat protein possesses DNA binding properties to function similar to BR1 nuclear shuttler. In this study, the amino acid combinations that are necessary to impart virulence were investigated through the evolutionary relationship and Pfam (Pfam is a database of protein families which includes the annotations and multiple sequence alignments of those proteins, which are generated using hidden Markov models). The predicted Nuclear localization signals (NLS) of ToLCV coat protein shares more similarity with experimentally known TYLCV coat protein NLS as cited in literature. Further, sequence and structure based approaches are needed for the

Fig. 2 : The member BR1 has been found to be the protein pre-dominantly present in *CP* gene of ToLCNDV of ridge gourd

Reformat		Format: Compact Hypertext	Row Display: up to 10	Color Bits: 2.0 bit	Type Selection: the most diverse members
Q08595	2	RRGAYTPR. [13].GKGR. [3].SYRRRGP. [2].PLARR. [7].ARAFYTKT. [7].PDFTIH. [1].NNYKSSYISMP	83	Indian cassava mosaic virus	
CAL30139	5	KSKGKRKR. [8].WKGA. [3].RRKTQYK. [2].PVRPP	ALCVLRQQ. [6].QSVVVT	NTPRIDLITCF	72 Oat dwarf virus
Q89238	8	RKGKRRKL. [8].WKGA. [3].RRKQAYK. [2].PVKPP	ALCVFRYN. [6].TNIIVG	NTPRVDLITCF	75 Wheat dwarf virus
Q39520	8	KRRKRSGG. [1].SKAK. [3].SSSYIPR. [2].SSRRE	SLQVATFS. [5].SGIKFS	PGGAAYLVSNF	67 Bean yellow dwarf virus
P31616	12	RKRGRYGG. [8].SQRE. [3].LVNQPR. [2].SNRRP	ALQVAEYL. [5].TGMTFS	PGGSTFLITNF	78 Tobacco yellow dwarf vir...
P14985	9	RKRPSSSS	AQAS. [3].RVYRPAV. [2].SLARR. [1].PLVQDFV. [2].TDVAFN	RGGGCYLLTSY	65 Chloris striate mosaic v...
Q76QL8	6	RKRGDSDN. [7].KKPS. [2].GLKRAGS	KADRP	SGGVCOLLINTY	67 Maize streak virus - [Re...
Q67566	7	RKRTDEGS. [7].KKSA	AKGRTSS. [1].RAIRP	TGGVCHLLSSY	67 Digitaria streak virus
Q89551	8	RKRSDTEG. [7].VKQG. [2].SAARAGS. [2].RRTRP	SLQIQLTQ. [4].SMIEVP	SGGVCOLLGSF	71 Sugarcane streak virus - ...
Q84369	7	RKRSEVA. [7].KKQD. [3].PLPRAGP. [2].RRGLP	ALQIQLTL. [4].TMITVP	SGGICSLIGTY	71 Panicum streak virus - K...
Q08595	84	VKTRA. [1].SDNRVGDYIKLVNISFTGTVCIKNSQMESDGS. [6].GLFTCVLRDKTPRI. [1].SAT. [4].PFP	153	Indian cassava mosaic virus	
CAL30139	73	AAGKG	DDNRHTNQITPMYKFLQGSVYVADASSKFVTP	LRLYHNLVDAEPKQ. [1].MPG	IED 131 Oat dwarf virus
Q89238	76	AQGKA	DDNRHTNQTVLYKFNIGQTCYMSDASAPFIEGP	LRVYHNLVDAEPKQ. [1].MPD	ATD 134 Wheat dwarf virus
Q39520	68	PQGAN	DNCRHTNKTVLYKFKMANTIYLDSSHYMKVFR	APFHFLVYDKSPGA. [1].VPS	TGD 126 Bean yellow dwarf virus
P31616	79	PQGAN	ENCRHTNRTITYKMAVKTWVALDGSFMFSRVSK	PFIYHNLVYDKNPG. [1].NPS	PSA 137 Tobacco yellow dwarf virus...
P14985	66	ARGSA	ENQRKTAETITYKAVNLGCAISGTMQYQYIS	SRPVCWILVYDAAPT. [1].AVT	PKD 124 Chloris striate mosaic virus...
Q76QL8	68	ARGSD	EGNRHTSETLYKIAIDYHFVADAACRYSENT	GTGVMNLVYDTPGG. [1].APT	PQT 126 Maize streak virus - [Reun...
Q67566	68	SRGSG	EGDRHTNETVITYKAAFYHFSAAGPCAYSII	GVGVNLVYDAQPSG. [1].VPA	VD 126 Digitaria streak virus
Q89551	72	ARGSD	ENRHTNETIYKVALDYHFIATAACKYSSI	GTGVNLVYDAQPSG. [1].PPT	VKD 130 Sugarcane streak virus - [...
Q84369	72	ARGSD	ENRHTNETLTYKVALDYHFVATAACKYSSI	GVGVNLVYDAQPTG. [1].SPE	VKD 130 Panicum streak virus - Karino
Q08595	154	. [1].LFGS	INASYADLSIQDP. [3].RFTVIRQVSYPVNTEK. [7].KGTTRFG	GRYPINTSFKDDG	217 Indian cassava mosaic virus
CAL30139	132	IFTM. [1].WNVLPSTWIRRA. [3].RFVVKRKWHVDLVSDG. [15].VGKNIIVD. [1].MKFIKGLRVSTEW	204	Oat dwarf virus	
Q89238	135	IFTM. [1].WNLPLPSTWVQRA. [3].RFVVKRKWHVNLVTDG. [15].VGKNIIVD. [1].SKFFKGLRVSTEW	207	Wheat dwarf virus	
Q39520	127	IFEG. [3].FPHNPWHTVSRRA. [3].RFVVKKTHSCVVENSG. [15].PCNQKKS. [1].MKFFKRLGVSTEW	201	Bean yellow dwarf virus	
P31616	138	IFDS. [1].YDQDPGTHVTRN. [3].RFVVKKTHSCHLENSG. [15].PCYQNRH. [1].TKFFKRLGVSTEW	210	Tobacco yellow dwarf virus...	
P14985	125	IFGY. [3].LVNMPHTHKVARA. [3].RFVVKRRWVFTMESNG. [13].IPQSLPV. [1].MKFAKQLGVSTEW	197	Chloris striate mosaic virus	
Q76QL8	127	IFAY. [3].LKAWPATWIKVSRE. [3].RFVVKRRWLFNMETDG. [14].PCKRNIY. [1].HKFTSGLGVSTEW	200	Maize streak virus - [Reun...	
Q67566	127	IFPH. [3].LQSFYTHKVGRE. [3].RFVVKRRWCFMTEMNG. [14].PCKRSIV. [1].HKFATGLGVSTEW	200	Digitaria streak virus	
Q89551	131	IFPH. [3].LTAFFYTHKVGRE. [3].RFVVKRRWVFTMEVNG. [14].PCKRNIY. [1].HKFVTGLGVSTEW	204	Sugarcane streak virus - ...	
Q84369	131	IFPH. [3].LSAFFYTHKVGRE. [3].RFVVKRRWCFMTEMNG. [14].PCKKDIY. [1].HKFCTGLGVSTEW	204	Panicum streak virus - Ka...	
Q08595	218	. [1].SGDSSGLYSNTYKNAILVYY. [4].DVSSQLEMY	CKYVTRYIG	260	Indian cassava mosaic virus
CAL30139	205	MNTGDGKIGDIIKKGALYLVY. [4].GVTGDSAST. [11].CYFKSIGLQ	257	Oat dwarf virus	
Q89238	208	MNTGDGKIGDIIKKGALYLVY. [4].GVTGDSAST. [11].CYFKAIGIQ	260	Wheat dwarf virus	
Q39520	202	KNSATGDVGDIIKKGALYIVG	APSQKSDVY. [6].VYFKSVGNQ	245	Bean yellow dwarf virus
P31616	211	KNSSTGDVADIIKKGALYLVY	APGGGATVR. [6].MYFKSVGNQ	254	Tobacco yellow dwarf virus (strain Australia)
P14985	198	KNAEGDFDGIKKGALYLVY	APANGAVFV. [6].VYFKSVGNQ	241	Chloris striate mosaic virus
Q76QL8	201	KNVTDGGVGAIQRGAALYVYI	APGNGLTFT. [6].LYFKSVGNQ	244	Maize streak virus - [Reunion2]
Q67566	201	KNVTDGGVGSIIKKGALYVYI	APGSGIDFT. [6].MYFKSVGNQ	244	Digitaria streak virus
Q89551	205	KNVTDGGVGDIIKKGALYVYI	APGNGLDFT. [6].LYFKSVGNQ	248	Sugarcane streak virus - [Natal]
Q84369	205	KNVTDGGVGAIIKKGALYVYI	APGNGLFT. [6].LYFKSVGNQ	248	Panicum streak virus - Karino

Fig. 5 : Comparison of amino acid sequence Geminivirus coat protein/nuclear export factor BR1 family with other viruses with respect to amino acid sequence

be interpreted as the evolutionary mechanism for the production of slightly different protein as a result of mutation to combat resistance.

The systemic spread of the ToLCNDV virus is assisted by the CP gene. The Coat protein of ToLCNDV are involved in the movement of the virus and their absence results in reduced levels of ssDNA that affects the systemic infection and symptom development in plants (Padidam *et al.*, 1995). ToLCNDV has been reported in Cucurbitaceae family in crops such as cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.), melon (*Cucumis melo* L.), watermelon [*Citrullus lannatus* (Thunb.)], bottle gourd [*Lagenaria siceraria* (Molina) standl.], sponge and ridge gourds (*Luffa* spp), bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia* L.), wax gourd [*Benincasa hispida* (Thunb.) Cogn.] and pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima* Duch.) (Chang *et al.*, 2010, Jyothsna *et al.*, 2013 and Bandaranayake

et al., 2014). The coat protein is also known for exclusively affecting the production/accumulation of MP (movement protein) in the plant cell and plays a significant role in the fast long-distance transfer of TMV throughout the plant (Hilf & Dawson, 1993 and Bendahmane *et al.*, 2002). The CP of ToLCNDV also interacts with a midgut protein of *B. tabaci* and probably facilitates virus transport both from the digestive tract to the haemolymph and from the hemolymph to the salivary glands (Rana *et al.*, 2016). ToLCNDV results in leaf curl disease in *Luffa acutangula* posing an important threat to its production. An effective control measure against ToLCNDV was lacking and no resistant variety of *Luffa acutangula* is available, the genetic transformation of *Luffa acutangula* was attempted in this study for providing resistance.

Transgenic approaches aim at enabling the production of durable and safe virus-resistant plants. However,

extensive field studies are needed for further assessment of this promising transgenic line. The CP gene was cloned into plant expression vectors pBI121. Subsequently, the confirmed pBI121 having CP gene construct was transformed into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. This is the first report of construction of the CP gene of ToLCNDV in pBI121 vector. It will be further used for transgenic plant development. The findings related to the *in-silico* approaches related to the CP gene will be further used for finding the exact virulence domain within the CP gene. This can be used further to establish a targeted approach in mitigating the virus.

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